

The Bogoliubov dispersion relation in a third-order nonlinear waveguide

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The quantum fluid of light has been an extensively studied phenomenon in cavity systems. A lot of experiments have been performed in planar microcavity geometries where the presence of strong light-matter coupling allowed the observation of its main features (Bose-Einstein Condensation (BEC) [1], superfluid flow [2], quantized vortices [3]). An alternative optical platform consists in bulk cavityless nonlinear media [4]-[6]. Here, it is well known that the complex amplitude of the optical field is a slowly varying function of space and time which satisfies a nonlinear Schrödinger equation. This latter relation, exchanging the roles played by time parameter and by the propagation coordinate, is mathematically identical (neglecting the losses) to the Gross-Pitaevskii equation of dilute atomic BEC. Exploiting such analogy the well known nonlinear optical phenomenon of Degenerate Four Wave Mixing (DFWM) can be reformulated in the language of the Bogoliubov theory of Bose matter superfluids [7]. As a result, the phase of the signal beam propagating in the nonlinear Kerr medium plays the role of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation of small excitations traveling on top of a weakly interacting BEC [7].

Here, we present an experimental approach to measure Bogoliubov dispersion relations in an optical Kerr medium. This dispersion is manifested in the Pump power and detuning dependence of the phase of the signal beam in a DFWM. The used platform is an integrated single mode Silicon (Si) or Silicon Nitride (Si_3N_4) waveguide. Indeed, the fabrication process allows designing specific waveguide geometries showing different values of the group velocity dispersion (GVD), which in analogy with the Gross-Pitaevskii equation [4], represents the photon effective mass. Different signs of the GVD can be achieved inside the same structure by exploiting the different polarization of the propagating Pump beam. As a result, stable and unstable regime of the luminous fluid can be investigated within the same device. As a side effect, the integration in an optical chip allows achieving a small effective mode area and increasing the accumulated phase by lengthening the waveguide. In order to perform stable and accurate phase measurements, a specific set-up has been implemented [8]. The set-up is based on a fully-automatized free-space Mach-Zhender interferometer, which allows to conduct degenerate Pump and Probe experiments. Slightly detuned Pump and Probe signals can be distinguished without any optical filter thanks to a lock-in amplifier.

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- [1] J. Kasprzak, M. Richard, et al., *Nature (London)* 443, 409 (2006).
 - [2] A. Amo, J. Lefrre, et al., *Nat. Phys.* 5, 805 (2009).
 - [3] G. Nardin, G. Grosso, et al., *Nat. Phys.* 7, 635 (2011).
 - [4] P.-É. Larré and I. Carusotto, *Phys. Rev. A* 91, 053809 (2015).
 - [5] P.-É. Larré and I. Carusotto, *Eur. Phys. J. D* 70, 45(2016).
 - [6] D. Vocke, K. E. Wilson, et al, *Phys. Rev. A* 94, 013849 (2016).
 - [7] P.-É. Larré, S. Biasi, et al., *Eur. Phys. J. D* 71, 6, p. 146, (2017).
 - [8] F. Turri, S. Biasi, et al., *IEEE TIM* pp. 1–9 (2018).